

more than saturated paddy. Flooding under puddled conditions was superior under all the soil-management practices. Under all water regimes, superphosphate was better than other phosphates. Farmyard manure gave better results in saturated conditions.

The phosphorus content due to superphosphate (0.103%) was significantly higher than that due to

rock phosphate (0.079%), yellow phosphorite (0.077%), and A.C. phosphorite (0.072%). Application of farmyard manure increased the phosphorus content, while various water regimes had no effect. Superphosphate application gave higher phosphorus content under all soil-management practices. Phosphorus uptake by paddy straw was significantly higher due to

superphosphate. The mean uptake was 44.6 mg/pot in superphosphate, followed by 27,23, and 23 mg/pot due to rock phosphate and yellow and ash-colored phosphorite. Lime application depressed the phosphorus uptake (20 mg/pot) and farmyard manure increased it (42 mg/pot). Flooded-puddled conditions increased phosphorus uptake.

Increasing rice yields under gall midge-infested conditions by increasing seedlings/hill

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Heavy gall midge infestation generally occurs during September and October in Northeast Thailand. The pest attacks only young rice buds and does not damage maturing rice plants. An experiment investigated whether rice yield under gall midge-infested conditions could be increased by increasing the number of rice seedlings. The experiment was designed in a split plot and replicated three times. Five rice varieties were studied: RD 9 and Meuy-Nong 62 M (resistant varieties), Kee-Tom-Laung (susceptible local variety), Dok-Ma-Li

105, and Niew-San-Pa-Tong (susceptible recommended varieties). Each variety was planted in a 6- × 12-sq-m-plot. The main plot was equally divided into three subplots where rice was transplanted at 3, 5, and 7 seedlings/hill. Gall midge-damaged tillers were observed at the peak of infestation (Sept. 14, 1976).

The percentage of damaged tillers did not significantly differ among hills with different numbers of seedlings (see table). In most cases, the average number of tillers and panicles significantly differed within each variety. Rice planted at 5 and 7 seedlings/hill produced more tillers and panicles than rice planted at 3 seedlings/hill. Overall mean rice yields did not differ significantly, probably because some varieties were resistant to gall midge and infestation on susceptible varieties was not heavy. However, the poor-tillering variety Kee-Tom-Laung

gave higher yields at 5 and 7 seedlings/hill than at 3 seedlings/hill.

Effect of root pruning and number of seedlings per hill on the growth performance of BR3 and Habiganj Boro VI in Bangladesh

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During the boro season (Nov.—Apr.) in Bangladesh, farmers uproot seedlings by cutting the roots inside the soil or by pulling the seedlings without watering the seedbeds. To compensate for seedling mortality, the farmers transplant 5 or 6 seedlings/hill. This study was conducted to determine the effect of root pruning in relation to the number of seedlings per hill on the growth performance of BR3, a semidwarf rice, and of Habiganj Boro VI (HbjB VI), a traditional variety with long droopy leaves.

All seedlings recovered at the same time, whether or not their roots were pruned. Both the pruned and unpruned seedlings produced considerable roots. Pruned seedlings of HbjB VI produced more roots than the unpruned seedlings, but in BR3 unpruned seedlings produced more roots than the pruned seedlings. Root production per seedling decreased as the number of seedlings per hill increased. In both varieties, the relative tillering rate (RTR) decreased as seedlings per hill increased. The RTR value of HbjB VI dropped sharply as the number of days after transplanting increased, but that of BR3 changed less drastically during the early stage. The difference may indicate that the RTR value of a variety depends on its plant

Gall midge infestation, yield components, and grain yields of five rice varieties at different numbers of seedlings per hill at Phibun Mangsahan, Ubon Ratchatani, Thailand, 1976.

Treatment		Damaged tillers (%)	Tillers (no./hill)	Panicles (no./hill)	Grains (no./panicle)	Yield (t/ha)
Kee-Tom-Laung	3 seedlings	15.5	7.4	5.2	68	1.3
KeeTom-Laung	5 seedlings	10.6	8.5	5.8	81	1.6
Kee-Tom-Laung	7 seedlings	15.5	10.0	6.1	81	1.7
RD 9	3 seedlings	1.6	11.8	11.6	62	1.3
RD 9	5 seedlings	2.3	15.5	12.5	56	1.4
RD 9	7 seedlings	1.2	13.8	12.2	57	1.3
Meuy-Nong 62 M	3 seedlings	2.8	10.6	6.5	83	1.6
Meuy-Nong 62 M	5 seedlings	2.8	9.6	7.3	79	1.7
Meuy-Nong 62 M	7 seedlings	3.6	11.2	8.6	77	1.8
Dok-Ma-Li 105	3 seedlings	12.7	13.2	9.0	85	2.0
Dok-Ma-Li 105	5 seedlings	13.8	13.9	9.3	87	1.9
Dok-Ma-Li 105	7 seedlings	17.9	15.7	10.5	89	2.0
Niew-San-Pa-Tong	3 seedlings	13.5	7.4	6.0	102	1.6
Niew-San-Pa-Tong	5 seedlings	17.1	10.6	6.9	101	1.7
Niew-San-Pa-Tong	7 seedlings	13.1	11.8	7.5	102	1.8
LSD (5%)		n.s. ^a	1.79	0.58	n.s. ^a	n.s. ^a

^aNot significant.